

EXCHANGE MECHANISMS IN DISTRIBUTED SIMULATION OF SOCIOTECHNICAL SYSTEMS

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Abstract

Growing variety and complexity of systems determines the important rule of the simulation, because specification possibilities of classical analytical methods are quite limited. The designing of heterogeneous simulation models is still difficult. One of the reasons is lack of suitable techniques for communications and synchronization of the various models inside the joint systems model. Some different methods and technologies (HLA etc.) exist. The author's discusses the CORBA (Common Object Request Broker Architecture) solution use for integration of the different separate models operating inside the goal model of the heterogeneous system.

Keywords: Simulation, sociotechnical systems, heterogeneous models, CORBA, HLA, EXTEND, NetLogo.

Introduction

Changes in thinking and understanding supported by the growing computational performance allow approximating the actors of engineering and social knowledge step by step. Although with displeasure, they must confess that analysis and operation of the real sociotechnical systems, especially stochastic, cannot be substantial without equal notice of both technical factors and social (environmental, biologic) phenomena.

The technical systems are mostly closed, but self-organization and changes in the structure of the model during the session are not typical for them. Unlike the social systems, whose are cognitive and the result of the activity can depend on the new knowledge obtained during the previous iteration and huge amount of important perturbations and inputs. Serious amount of simulation tools and simulators are created for modelling technical as well as social systems allowing to design continuous, discrete, time-driven, event-driven and other models, nevertheless designing of heterogeneous simulation models is still difficult due to lack techniques for communications and synchronization.

As one of the typical samples existing HLA (High Level Architecture) can be mentioned. HLA serves as standard solution for distributed simulation, but if simulation environment have not been designed to be compatible with HLA *a priori*, then it application is problematic, therefore as one of suitable solutions the CORBA (Common Object Request Broker Architecture) solution for integration of the different separate models operating inside the goal model can be used.

1. THE HETEROGENEOUS SIMULATION MODEL OF THE TOURISM OBJECT

The Ligatne Natural Trails [1] was founded in 1975 as an integrated tourism object for recreation and ecosystems research giving possibility for introduction with flora and fauna, which is typical for Latvian regions. There exist different routes for the visitors either by foot or by car. The total amount of visitors and cars are permanently growing. This asks for expanding of parking and traffic dispatching. Permanently growing amount of visitors makes pressure on functioning of ecosystem and regeneration possibilities of lawns in sightseeing places. Therefore, potential workload forecasting of the tourism object, which depending of tourists flows intensity, becomes important. In 2006 two separate simulation models [2] were elaborated, which involves logistics model described as discrete-event system and written in EXTEND and the model for regenerating possibilities forecasting specified as agent-based systems and designed in NetLogo (see Fig. 1). The models are provided for advising the operator-manager of the logistics system of the Ligatne Natural Trails.

The logistics schema consists of the set of routes with places for parking the cars. The total amount of parking places is limited. Therefore, only limited amount of cars can enter the park. The tourists travelling by cars are going until free chosen parking place and then attending the sightseeing places for animals watching. Capacity of sightseeing places also is limited even more exceeding the regeneration possibilities of the natural resources (lawns, for instance) is restricted. The regeneration possibilities depend on meteorological factors (temperature, humidity) and intensity of tourist's flow. The logistics model allows planning the parking places and generates input for NetLogo model aimed for regeneration possibilities forecasting. The trail manager respecting the outputs of the models can decides about limiting the cars and tourists flow entering the tourism object.

Fig. 1. Heterogeneous advising system of the trail manager

The task of the communication system is intensity data transfer from the logistics model to the environmental model of the object in real-time. There some different techniques can be used, but respecting some specific criterions as time, safety and cost of the solution. Safety and time are not critical because real-time demands in this case are flexible and safety of the data transfers is the same. Critical is solutions cost, because non-profit application is observed. It means that performance, of course, is important,

while the price is critical, therefore HLA introduction would be unfortunately problematic [3]. Nevertheless, some other solutions can be used (ALSP, CORBA, FIPA etc.) [4, 5, 6].

2. CORBA - COMMON OBJECT REQUEST BROKER ARCHITECTURE FOR DISTRIBUTED COMMUNICATION IN HETEROGENEOUS MODELS

The CORBA [7] can be considered as one of most universal and wide spread application for information exchange in distributed software environment, but this solution seems to be used also for other objects communications support.

The main element in the CORBA architecture is Object Request Broker (ORB), which provides a mechanism for transparently communicating of the clients. The ORB simplifies distributed programming by decoupling the client from the details of the method invocations, because the ORB is responsible for finding the object implementation, transparently activating it, delivering the request to the object, and returning any response to the client (see Fig.2).

Fig. 2. ORB based communication in heterogeneous model

In this architecture two objects communicate, one of them is *servant*, but other is *client*. In Ligatne Trail model the servant is logistics model working in EXTEND environment, but client is environmental model operating in NetLogo. The EXTEND extension is written in C++, but NetLogo supplements – in Java (see Fig. 3).

The servant operates in following order:

- Creates and initializes the ORB object for interface needs;
- Receives the reference to Portable Object Adapter (POA) and activates POA. The POA issues references on the objects announced by servant. Client by these references can find the necessary object and uses the functions of the object;
- The servant is registered in the ORB object;
- Receives the reference to the servant registered;
- The main *Naming Service* is clarified. The *Naming Service* ensures converting the reference of the servant in textual form. Client can use the Naming Service for the reference resolving;

- Records the link and the name of servant in Naming Service;
- Waiting for client request.

Fig.3. CORBA client's communication algorithm

The client operates in following order:

- Creates and initializes the ORB object for interface needs;
- The main *Naming Service* is clarified;
- Receives the reference from the *Naming Service* and necessary servant;
- By the reference can request the procedures of the servant.

The practical implementation approves that CORBA architecture can be used for the current distributed simulation model communication needs, but performance research and comparison with other tools (HLA etc.) is the next task.

Conclusions

The analysis of the sociotechnical systems determines the heterogeneous simulation models use. Because interdisciplinary knowledge and tools are necessary then modelling is inconvenient. Mainly the representatives of engineering direction vote for the technical systems modelling environment use, but great part of the representatives coming from social sciences possibilities of simulation and quantitative analysis raise the light surprise.

One of the main elements in heterogeneous system is communication subsystem, which support the data exchange and synchronising the processes. The functionality, performance parameters and safety are important. The different tools are exist HLA, CORBA etc, nevertheless estimation the availability each of the methods is important. The authors of the Ligatne Natural Trails tourism object management system recommends the CORBA solution use, because safety and performance parameters weight in total integrated criterion for estimation of the communication subsystem is not critical.

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